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TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Integrated Comparative Risk Assessment

Deliverable 2.5

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present work provides an innovative integrated climate risk assessment covering the entire European domain at NUTS 2 resolution and focusing on five socio-economic sectors relevant to the TransformAr mission, namely agriculture, fishery, tourism, coastal flooding and river flooding. The assessment focuses on two opposite future emission scenarios (ssp126 and ssp585) and two future periods (2015-2045 and 2035-2065), defining the most impacted regions as those showing the strongest negative variation in sectorial productivity and damage losses compared to the historical period. With respect to the traditional IPCC approach, the hazard component of climate risk is replaced with the “intermediate impact” produced by climate change on the studied sectors and calculated by dedicated bio-physical models. This approach allows to have a more comprehensive and integrated estimate of the bio-physical effects of climate change on the studied systems compared to assessing the impacts through single climatic risk drivers. Differences between single climate risk drivers as hazards and using intermediate impact through biophysical methods are key element of uncertainty in the evaluation for policy makers and available across different risk assessment products in the project. The regional socio-economic exposure and vulnerability are estimated through a range of indicators and combined with the intermediate impact to produce the risk assessment. The results point out a substantial north-south gradient of climate risk. The principal cause of this risk imbalance across the continent is the gap in exposure and vulnerability, with southern European regions scoring less in most of the socio-economic, technological and institutional parameters used in the assessment. River flooding is an exception to this trend, as it is strongly related to the location of major streams and assets making it more significant in central and eastern Europe. A second source of risk inequality is identified between coastal and land-locked regions, with the former generally having a higher aggregated climate risk due to the impacts of climate change on fishery and coastal flooding in addition to the other sectorial risks.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Description
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
COACCH	Co-designing the Assessment of Climate CHange costs
EU	European Union
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ESPON	European Territory Observation Network
EUCRA	European Climate Risk Assessment
GVA	Gross Value Added
ISIMIP	Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project
KCS	Key Community System
PPS	Purchasing Power Standards
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
WP	Work Package
Participant acronym	Description
UA	University of Antwerp
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change
ACTERRA	Acterra
E3M	E3-Modelling
PIK	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
VERHAERT	Verhaert
FEUGA	Fundación Empresa-Universidad Gallega
NCSR	National Center for Scientific Research “Demokritos”
CZU	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague
LUT	LUT University
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
UVIGO	University of Vigo
EPSILON	EPSILON
ADEME	ADEME Guadeloupe
WRT	Westcountry Rivers Trust
MEDSEA	Mediterranean Sea and Coast Foundation
CETMAR	Fundación CETMAR: Centro Tecnológico del Mar
LAPP	Lappeenranta Municipality
MOE	Egaleo Municipality
WE	Water Europe
EQY	Euroquality
MOG	Municipality of Gjøvik

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TransformAr – Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages – is an H2020 project funded under the H2020 Programme, coordinated by the University of Antwerp (UA).

The TransformAr project, launched on October 1st 2021, precisely aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The project, funded by the EU Research and Innovation Programme Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement No 101036683, gathers 22 partnering organisations from 11 Member States. It has an overall budget of approximately €12 million and will run for 4 years, between October 2021 and September 2025.

1. Introduction

Over the last decade, there has been a rapid surge in the number of climate risk assessments, spanning from the local to the regional scale (Gallina et al., 2016; Menk et al., 2022; Ye et al., 2021). Despite the increasing abundance of relevant publications, a common definition of climate change risk is not yet available, with different approaches followed in the IPCC reports and by national-level assessments. Simpson et al., (2021) classified existing integrated risk assessments in three categories of increasing complexity (Table 1). The most common type of assessment considers a combination of hazard, exposure and vulnerability to define a climate risk (level 1). While this approach facilitates the risk definition and helps identifying its most direct drivers, its simplicity limits the accuracy and comprehensiveness of risk definition. In contrast, more complex assessments (level 2 and 3) offer a holistic definition of climate risk opposed to a siloed list of drivers: risk and risk components result from multiple interacting factors.

Table 1. Synthetic description of the most common frameworks of integrated risk assessments classified by the level of complexity by Simpson et al., (2021).

Level of complexity	Description
Level 1	<p>One driver for each of the risk components, with the relationship between the different components defining the overall risk.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ e.g., the impact of reduced precipitation on crops yield
Level 2	<p>Multiple drivers for each risk component</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ e.g., the hazard component for food security risk stems from changes in both precipitation and temperature ranges <p>Assesses both the interaction between drivers of the same risk component and between drivers of different components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ e.g., heatwaves increase the risk to food security by both leading to drought (increased hazard) and reduce the productivity of agricultural workers (increased vulnerability)
Level 3	<p>Considers the interaction between different risks to determine the overall risk for the system</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ e.g, risk of food insecurity creates a risk for social unrest <p>Identifies compound risks and cascading risks as those who trigger the insurgence of other risks in related and unrelated sectors</p>

This holistic definition of climate risk first appeared in the IPCC special reports leading to AR6. Since then, the same approach has been followed by national and regional climate risk assessments, with the US National Climate Assessment (Jay et al., 2023), the UK Climate Change Risk Assessment (Betts and Brown, 2021) and the European Climate Risk Assessment (EUCRA) (European Environment Agency,

2024) being some of the most ambitious examples. Analysing these works allows to gather the key common elements making up the state-of-the-art for integrated climate risk assessments. Indeed, while some minor differences in approach emerge, the methodological structure is largely coherent. The risk assessment is generally made up by three phases leading to the final determination of action urgency: the estimate of risk severity, the confidence analysis of risk severity and the evaluation of policy readiness. The first phase aims at identifying major climate risks for the studied area (i.e., Europe for EUCRA) and classify them according to their potential for severe consequences. Risk is defined as the combination of hazard, exposure and vulnerability. The hazard component of risk is formed by both climate-driven hazards and non-climatic risk drivers, which interaction often leads to compound risk drivers (IPCC, 2022). Notably, considering non-climatic risk drivers aims at identifying the elements of legislation, technology and infrastructure that can contribute to the overall climate hazard by either reinforcing it (e.g., environmental stressors decreasing systems resilience) or having lock-in effects (e.g., outdated design standards of infrastructure). Contributing to the hazard component is also the effect of other risks on the system, usually referred to as ‘cascading risk’. The exposure component includes all the elements of a system that can be affected by the hazard, such as people, ecosystems, physical assets and economic sectors. Finally, the vulnerability component of risk encompasses the well-established components of sensitivity and adaptive capacity. From the combination of these components, risk severity is estimated using quantitative thresholds of impact. The thresholds are expressed in terms of economic loss (monetary or GDP percentage), affected population or other losses (e.g., land losses, losses of species, loss of historical heritage) and are aimed at making risk magnitude comparable across different systems and impacts. Once risk severity has been assessed, a confidence assessment is undertaken to weight the robustness of the risk drivers and the effects produced by their interaction. Finally, the last phase of the assessment consists of an evaluation of the current policy scenario related to the studied risk. The current policy status is used to determine the urgency of further action based on the risk severity assessment. In EUCRA, the policy analysis also serves to identify the risk ownership (i.e., where major responsibility of risk management lies) and the policy horizon (i.e., the timeframe on which future action will have to be based, longer meaning a longer-term risk). From the combination of the risk severity assessment and confidence analysis with the policy status evaluation, an assessment of urgency of action for each of the studied risks is produced.

While providing a state-of-the-art risk assessment on the continental scale, EUCRA scope is not to assess climate risk on the sub-regional scale. EUCRA was released in 2024 and aimed at expanding the IPCC AR6 results for Europe by assessing the most relevant climate-related risks at continent scale and identifying those requiring the most urgent action (EEA, 2024). In fact, the aim is to inform policy makers at EU level, with the adaptation measures stemming from it having continental relevance. In this sense, EUCRA does not offer a representation of climate risk distribution across the continent. It is mentioned that some of the analysed risks are more relevant for some European countries than others, but the assessment does not identify critical areas within the countries. While it is important to identify the overarching risks for the continent, these might not be relevant everywhere. On one hand, some risk drivers are only applicable to certain contexts: the risk of coastal flooding only affects coastal countries. On the other, the same risk driver can have varying degrees of impact at the sub-national scale due to the concomitant gradients in exposure, vulnerability and adaptive capacity.

From this heterogeneity in the way climate risk affects human systems stems the need for disaggregated risk assessments focusing on smaller, more homogeneous spatial units. For reasons of comparability and data availability, previous works focusing on Europe have used the NUTS2 and NUTS3 regions as the units of intra-EU climate risk assessments. One of the earliest works was the ESPON-CLIMATE project, which aimed at analysing the impact of climate change on the competitiveness and cohesion of European regions (Navarro et al., 2022). The first assessment was performed in 2011, with updated versions released in 2014 and 2022. The latest version focused on seven impact chains, in which the risk posed from a particular climate hazard to a specific group or sector was analysed at NUTS3 level, an example being the impact of drought on agriculture (Navarro et al., 2022).

While relatively recent, even the latest ESPON assessment is based on some dated elements. First, the risk methodology is the one set out in the IPCC AR5, so it does not consider the important advancement in the definition of climate risk frameworks made with AR6 and the special reports leading to it described above. In addition, the climate-driven hazard component is based on the older generation of global climate models (CMIP5), that generally shows a weaker global warming signal than the latest generation (CMIP6), thus affecting the risk severity assessment (Cos et al., 2022; Palmer et al., 2021). Furthermore, by only assessing the impacts of one type of hazard on a specific sector, ESPON provides a relatively simple description of sectorial risk (i.e., level 1 assessment in Table 1) not accounting for the multiple concomitant risk drivers brought by climate change.

This work builds on the methodology of the ESPON reports to produce a more comprehensive risk assessment at NUTS-2 level analysing how different key socio-economic sectors will be affected by the change in mean climatic conditions brought by varying levels of global warming (i.e., approaching a level 2 risk assessment). ESPON, an EU funded programme steered by the Joint Research Center and the European Environmental Agency, represents a reference point for European policy for adaptation to climate change and is aligned with several European initiatives to bridge research with policies. The ESPON approach and methodologies have been traditionally applied in many studies related to vulnerability assessments (ESPON 2022). In this work, we ensure methodological approach that could mark continuity and comparability with the former ESPON-CLIMATE risk assessments, while providing several updates. The main element of novelty is the use of sector-specific biophysical modelling tools to ground the assessment on quantitative “intermediate impacts” of climate change rather than qualitatively aggregating a limited range of climate variables to derive the climatic forcing component. Additionally, this update provides a revision of data sources using the latest CMIP6 climate runs and incorporation of new variables, better aligned with recent updates in the climate adaptation resources in Europe. Therefore, by integrating different methodological aspects from existing works and introducing new elements for impact quantification, this work represents a novel contribution for the European context.

2. Methodology

2.1 Risk Framework

The risk framework adopted in this work moves slightly away from the standard IPCC categorization identifying risk as the combination of hazard, exposure and vulnerability. The main difference is the replacement of the climatic hazard component with the damage assessment produced in D2.3 as the starting point. The results of D2.3 are sectorial bio-physical damages resulting from a deeply integrated, quantitative combination of hazard, exposure and sensitivity components performed by dedicated biophysical models. Thus, the use of these data as the foundation of the risk assessment allows to have a more integrated and accurate representation of the effects of climate change on each sector than simply aggregating a few climate variables to produce a hazard index. Moreover, this approach allows to capture the effects of mean climatic changes on the respective sectors rather than focusing on changes in specific climate indices linked to an extreme weather event as done in previous other works (Navarro et al., 2022). In this way, the contribution of different hazards to risk generation is inherently imbedded in the risk assessment and grounded on the quantitative integration of hazard components provided by the biophysical models (Simpson et al., 2021).

The bio-physical damages produced by D2.3 are used as “intermediate impacts”, representing the impacts that climate change will have on each studied sector independently from the socio-economic dimension (Menk et al., 2022). Intermediate impacts are here defined as the future change in each NUTS2 region sectorial productivity (for agriculture, fishery and tourism) or expected damage (for river and coastal flooding) compared to historical conditions. As illustrated by Figure 1, the intermediate impact data will then be combined with socio-economic exposure and vulnerability data to produce an integrated risk index. In line with D2.3, the assessment focuses on the risks for agriculture, fishery, tourism, river flooding and coastal flooding at NUTS2 level.

The final risk index is expressed with increasing 1-5 (no risk, low, medium, high, very high) categories. The final risk score results from the geometric mean of the ranks of the intermediate impact, exposure and vulnerability components (figure 1). The use of a geometric mean appears and is similarly established in the integrated climate risk assessments for the ESPON-CLIMATE regional risk assessment for Europe, among other similar risk assessments. The use of a weighted average approach could improve the relative relevance of the different risk assessment components (Becker et al., 2017 ; Papatoma-Kohle et al., 2019 ; Magnan et al., 2025) . However, assigning weights also poses the risk of an inaccurate representation of real conditions if these are assigned arbitrarily and ignoring the causal relations among the variables considered (Nardo et al 2008), especially considering the large spatial scale and the heterogeneity of the sectors and regions across the studied area. The risk components are ranked based on their increasing contribution to risk, with damages, exposure and sensitivity being directly related to risk and adaptive capacity being inversely related to it.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the methodology used to derive the risk index from the combination of intermediate impact, socio-economic exposure and vulnerability for each of the studied sectors. The black dots along the arrows indicate ranking of data to allow comparability; the red dots indicate when the geometric mean of the ranked indicators is computed, with the arrows showing the results. The combination of the climate hazard with the biophysical sensitivity to produce the biophysical damages for each sector was performed in D2.3.

2.2 Data sources

Table 2 illustrates the raw datasets used to calculate the sectorial damages in D2.3 along with the final product of the calculations for each sector. Raw data for agriculture and fishery were sourced from the biophysical models of the ISIMIP platform based on bias-corrected CMIP6 climate projections (ISIMIP3b¹). In particular, the impact on agriculture was estimated from the regional change in yield of six common European crops (maize, potato, rice, sorghum, soy and winter wheat) weighted for their respective harvested area. The impact on fishery was based on the regional changes in total fish catch. For tourism, data on bed night stays were sourced from Matei et al., (2023), while data on river and coastal flooding come from the COACCH project (Bosello et al., 2020). The future emission pathways considered in the damage assessments were SSP1.26 and SSP5.85 in the periods 2015-2045 (mean around 2030) and 2035-2065 (mean around 2050). The only exception is the tourism sector, for which data were only available for the 2035-2065 period. In this way, a total of four scenarios (two for tourism) spanning short- and medium-term impacts under low and high emission conditions were analysed. The reference historical period considered is 1985-2015 (mean around 2000) for agriculture and fishery, 2019 for tourism and 2010 for river flooding. Historical data were not available for coastal flooding, thus expected damages under SSP126 for the year 2020 were used as the baseline to calculate changes.

¹ <https://www.isimip.org/>
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Future projections for the exposure and vulnerability indicators were not available, so averaged data from the last decade (2012-2022) were considered representative of current conditions and kept fixed into the future. Socio-economic exposure data were included in the assessment to have a more realistic representation of the impact of bio-physical damages on the wider public and a more accurate estimate of the inter-regional risk differences. In this perspective, the sectorial Gross Value Added (GVA) and employment rate were identified as the most suitable parameters to capture the regional socio-economic implications of climate change impact on agriculture, fishery and tourism (table 2). In line with ESPON methodology, the sectorial indicators were scaled according to their total equivalents to identify their relative importance in the region economy (Navarro et al., 2022). Additional exposure indicators were not identified for river and coastal flooding as impact data for these sectors were already available in monetary terms, with the combination of biophysical impact and economic exposure already performed within the COACCH project (Bosello et al., 2020).

In line with the latest IPCC definition, vulnerability is considered as the combination of impact sensitivity and adaptive capacity. Vulnerability indicators were selected to include metrics of social, technological, infrastructural, economic and institutional sensitivity (table 2). Some indicators were substituted for similar counterparts with respect to the ESPON approach. These include the gender equality index, here represented by the gender employment gap, and the regional GDP, here substituted by the regional household disposable income. Moreover, one indicator of economic capacity and two of institutional capacity not included in ESPON were used in this assessment. The former is the Gini coefficient, which represents a measure of wealth inequality within a territory (De Maio, 2007). The latter two are the Coping Capacity Index, representing the ability of institutions to implement disaster risk reduction activities (UNDRR, 2022), and the Quality of Government Index, which is based on people perception of governance in different critical aspects such as the level of corruption or the effectiveness in policy making (Charron et al., 2024). These indicators were added to increase the significance of institutional capacity within the assessment, as the improvement of institutional conditions has been often identified as the driver for progress in all other aspects of adaptive capacity to climate change (IPCC, 2022).

Table 2. Indicators used in the sectorial integrated risk assessments for the intermediate impact, socio-economic exposure and vulnerability components. The intermediate impact and exposure indicators are sector-specific, while the same indicators have been used to represent vulnerability for all the sectors.

Sector	Agriculture		Fishery		Tourism		River flooding	Coastal flooding
Intermediate impact								
Metric	Yield change (%)		Total catch change (%)		Bed nights change (%)		Expected annual damage (EUR)	Expected annual damage (EUR)
Source	D2.3		D2.3		D2.3		COACCH	COACCH
Socio-economic exposure								
Metric	Sector GVA	Employ rate	Sector GVA	Employ rate	Sector GVA	Employ rate	-	-
Source	EUROSTAT		EUROSTAT		EUROSTAT		-	-
Vulnerability								
Capacity	Metric		Unit			Source		
Economic	Employment rate		% total population			EUROSTAT		
	Household disposable income		Million PPS			EUROSTAT		
	Poverty risk		% total population			EUROSTAT		
	Gini coefficient		Unitless			Risk Data Hub		
Infrastructure and technology	Hospital beds		% of total population			EUROSTAT		
	R&D expenditure		Million PPS			EUROSTAT		
	Researchers employed		% of total employed			EUROSTAT		
Social	Education expenditure		Million PPS			EUROSTAT		
	Gender employment gap		%			EUROSTAT		
	Students in tertiary education		% of total population			EUROSTAT		
Institutional	Population covered by the Covenant of Mayors		%			EUROSTAT		
	Quality of government index		Unitless			Charron et al. (2024)		
	Coping capacity index		Unitless			Risk Data Hub		

2.3 Data processing

2.3.1 Impacts

Intermediate impact data were ranked from 1 to 5 based on quantiles of increasing damage among EU NUTS2 regions. Thus, the highest rank was assigned to the regions suffering the highest relative impact (i.e., an increase of the level of impacts compared to the current situation), not those suffering the highest absolute damage. In this way, the assessment highlights which regions will experience the most significant worsening of their current condition due to climate change.

For coastal and river flood, damage in each NUTS2 region was ranked based on which of the 20th percentile classes it belonged to (i.e., damage in 80th to 100th percentile has a rank of 5). Regions experiencing a reduction in the relative flooding damages were classified as “low impact” since, albeit smaller than historical, they are still suffering some damages. A different approach was applied to agricultural, fishery and tourism impacts, as some regions experienced an improvement in their condition in these sectors with climate change. For these sectors, the improvement is not a mere reduction of losses (as for flooding), but it represents a gain in the sector productivity. Therefore, the positively impacted regions were considered “not impacted” if their gain was greater than the 10th percentile of the gaining regions (i.e., calculated not considering the regions with negative impacts). In contrast, positively impacted regions with gains lower than the 10th percentile were given a “low impact” score to account for uncertainties in the biophysical models. Negatively impacted regions were then assigned to the medium, high and very high categories if their damage was smaller than the 60th percentile, within the 60th and 80th percentile or greater than the 80th percentile of the damaged regions, respectively. Table 2 offers a schematic example of how the ranking works in the context of the agricultural sector. For all sectors, the percentile classes were calculated on the damage sample of all the four scenarios to avoid smoothing of the climate change signal.

Table 2. Example of the ranking method of biophysical impacts, here the agricultural sector is shown for reference.

Region	Impact - Future yield change (%)	Impact percentile	Impact rank
A	+5	>10 th of + values	0 - No impact
B	+0.2	<10 th of + values	2 - Low
C	-0.3	0-60 th of - values	3 - Medium
D	-2	60-80 th of - values	4 - High
E	-10	>80 th of - values	5 - Very high

2.3.2 Exposure and Vulnerability

The same ranking procedure used for flooding impacts and based on increasing 20th percentile classes was also applied to the employment and GVA indicators used to represent the socio-economic exposure of the agriculture, fishery and tourism sectors (Figure 2). Exposure for agriculture and fishery was considered the same, as it is only available as an aggregated dataset at NUTS2 level. The geometric mean of the employment and GVA ranks was used to produce the socio-economic exposure indicator.

The same ranking procedure was applied to the individual vulnerability indicators. In line with ESPON methodology, a single vulnerability index was used to represent regional vulnerability to climate change rather than having individual vulnerability indices for each sector. Vulnerability is a cross-sectorial dimension of climate change risk, with the different components influencing each other to define the overall level of preparedness to face climate impacts. The regional vulnerability index was calculated as the geometric mean of the ranked parameters (Figure 3), with all parameters assigned equal weight. The resulting index was then used as the vulnerability component in all the impact chain risk assessments. The vulnerability indicators were chosen to represent the overall level of preparedness of regions against climate related hazards. The indicators align with those chosen in the ESPON 2022 assessment (Navarro et al., 2022), which sectorial coverage aligns with the one of the present study.

Different from sectorial vulnerability is the identification of the different dimensions making up the overall vulnerability. Figure 4 shows a breakdown of the different thematic components of vulnerability considered in this study, namely institutional, infrastructural, social and economic. The division of the different vulnerability components helps understanding how different NUTS2 regions might be impacted and respond to different types of biophysical stressors. For instance, regions with high economic vulnerability are more sensitive to climate change impacts having direct financial repercussions, as their economy is not sufficiently resilient to absorb them. Similarly, regions with high institutional vulnerability are particularly threatened by climate change impacts that might cause widespread social unrest, like droughts causing water shortages, as their governing bodies might struggle to quickly and effectively respond to the emergency. In addition, this division favours the comparison between regional vulnerability and some of the Sustainable Development Goals of the UN 2030 Agenda. For instance, the institutional vulnerability index presented in figure 4 offers a good indication on the level of attainment of some crucial indicators of SDG13 (Climate Action) and SDG16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions). Similarly, the economic vulnerability indicator is composed by metrics (table 3) that are directly related to those indicated to measure progress in SDG1 (No Poverty) and SDG8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth).

Figure 2. Socio-economic exposure of the agriculture and fishery sectors (a) and the tourism sector (b) at NUTS2 level. The exposure ranking is given by the combination of sectorial employment and GVA data scaled to their total counterparts. Data sourced from EUROSTAT.

VULNERABILITY

Figure 3. Vulnerability index at NUTS2 level resulting from the combination of the sensitivity and adaptive capacity indicators listed in Table 2.

Figure 4. Institutional, infrastructural, social and economic vulnerability components at NUTS2 level resulting from the combination of the respective indicators as grouped in Table 2.

2.3.3 Risk

Once the intermediate impact, exposure and vulnerability components were processed and ranked, the sectorial risk index was calculated as the geometric mean of the three components (Figure 1).

Finally, an aggregated risk index was produced combining the sectorial risk indexes through a geometric mean, with 'not at risk' sectors being assigned a score of 1. For all regions, the aggregation process entailed combining the impact and exposure ranks for each sector, then calculating the geometric mean of the resulting indices and the vulnerability index. In this way it was possible to aggregate the economic sectors (i.e., tourism, agriculture and fishery) with the flooding damages ensuring compatibility across different units of measure.

The choice of the ranking order (i.e., 5 = highest contribution to risk) leads to a conservative estimate of risk since geometric means tend to be skewed towards low values. The greatest bias is observed at the tails of the distribution, with negligible difference observed for the regions scoring at the centre of the distribution (medium and high risk). Given the limited number of sectors analysed, we believed that skewing the distribution towards the conservative end was a more reasonable approach, with more high-risk scores in the individual sectors needed to get an aggregated high-risk evaluation. Indeed, labelling a region with "very high" aggregated climate change risk when only impacts on a few sectors are considered could lead to excessive alarmism. Yet, we are aware that the opposite is true and that a high number of low-risk regions could produce a false sense of optimism. Thus, we remind the reader that the present assessment focuses on a limited number of economic sectors and infrastructures strictly relevant to the scope of the TransformAr project and does not intend to provide an exhaustive assessment of regional climate risk. For a more detailed analysis of climate induced risk across Europe, the reader is referred to the EU Climate Risk Assessment (European Environment Agency, 2024).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Agriculture

Future changes in mean climatic conditions will not pose a threat to the overall agricultural production of most European regions (figure 5). This is because most central and northern European regions will experience an increase in crop yields, with bio-physical models projections suggesting that future climate conditions will be more suitable for the cultivation of the studied crops with respect to the historical period. This is mainly due to the projected increase in mean temperature, widening the growing season and the concomitant increase in mean precipitation rates (Hristov et al., 2020).

However, opposite conclusions can be drawn for southern Europe, with several regions around the Mediterranean projected at high to very high risk in all studied scenarios. This is the case of all regions in the south of Spain and Portugal (except Lisbon), as well as Sardinia in Italy, Ipeiros in northern Greece and Jadranska Hrvatska in Croatia (figure 5). The high-risk profile of these regions stems from the combination of projected reductions in crop yields with the high exposure of the primary sector (figure 2), as the economy of these regions is still highly dependent on agriculture, and the high vulnerability given by their overall infrastructural underdevelopment compared to the rest of Europe (figure 3) (Dijkstra et al., 2023). The reduction in yield is mainly driven by the declining precipitation rates, making rainfed cultivations suffering yield losses of up to 50% (see D2.3). Water scarcity in southern Europe also cancels out the beneficial effects of the future CO₂ concentration increase (i.e., CO₂ fertilization), which, in contrast, is likely to contribute to the increase in yields observed in northern Europe. Yet, the net effects of CO₂ fertilization on plants physiology are still debated and contribute to the uncertainty of the present results (Hristov et al., 2020). In addition, the high exposure and vulnerability make the agricultural sector in the whole Mediterranean region more susceptible to the effects of climate change than in northern Europe. An example of this greater Mediterranean sensitivity is given by the comparison of southern continental Italy and northern France in the SSP585 scenario (figure 5b and 5d). In 2030, both these areas are not at risk, but when climate change impacts appear in 2050, southern Italy is more severely impacted (mostly high risk) than northern France (medium risk). These results point out how the effects of climate change are not homogenous across Europe, but strong gradients in its socio-economic consequences can be observed even when its bio-physical impact is not significantly different (see D2.3). Consequently, regions with high exposure and vulnerability scores should implement adaptation strategies to reduce this gap with the rest of the continent.

Figure 5. Agriculture sector risk at NUTS2 level for the ssp126 and ssp585 scenarios in the years 2030 and 2050. Regions experiencing positive impacts are classified in the “no risk” category (white). Regions where data on either impact, exposure or vulnerability were not available are shown in grey.

3.2 Fishery

Differently from agriculture, climate change poses a more geographically homogeneous risk to fishery, with both northern and southern European regions affected (figure 6). However, the projections on the biophysical impact of climate change on fishery are subject to significant uncertainty due to the large variety of contributing factors and the approximations made in the model parameterization. In general, there is widespread agreement that tropical fisheries will suffer significant declines in productivity due to sea warming and acidification, while high latitude regions might experience an increase in total catches due to species migration (Cheung et al., 2016; Barange et al., 2018). Since large parts of Europe lie between the tropical and boreal latitudes, the impacts of climate change are variable and heavily dependent on location-specific ecological features. For instance, the decrease in total catches observed across multiple regions of the North Sea can be explained by the northward migration of boreal species that might not yet be compensated by the establishment of new subtropical species (Barange et al., 2018). In general, Mediterranean fisheries are likely to be more negatively impacted by climate change due to the sharp warming rates and the tropicalization effects

already visible, with invasive species further compromising the industry. Yet, recent regional studies point out how significant gradients in climate change impact appear even within the Mediterranean basin (Hidalgo et al., 2022; Pita et al., 2021), further suggesting that modelling projections based on global parameters have high uncertainty at the finer scales. Interestingly, in ssp126 northern Europe is projected to be more impacted than the Mediterranean, with most regions of the North and Baltic seas being at medium to high risk. Significantly higher risk is observed in ssp585 for southern Europe, in which hotspots of high to very high risk appears around the Black Sea and the Aegean Sea, as well as in Iberia. As in the case of agriculture, these results show how when negative bio-physical impacts occur, northern European regions are less likely to be heavily impacted due to their lower exposure and vulnerability.

Figure 6. Fishery sector risk at NUTS2 level for the ssp126 and ssp585 scenarios in the years 2030 and 2050. Regions experiencing positive impacts are classified in the “no risk” category (white). Regions where data on either impact, exposure or vulnerability were not available are shown in grey.

3.3 Tourism

A sharp north-south divide also applies to tourism risk, for which only mid-century projections are available (figure 7). In ssp585 only southern European regions will be at risk for a reduction in tourism fluxes, while central and northern Europe will experience more favourable climate conditions for tourist arrivals. Most central European regions considered at medium to high risk in ssp126 will not be at risk in the warmer scenario.

The results point out how the tourism sector across the whole Mediterranean basin will suffer from the effects of climate change, with the highest projected risk is found in the regions of southern Italy and in Romania. These risk-hotspot regions are those experiencing the highest projected negative impacts, which explain why they have a worse risk score than Iberia despite this area has the highest socio-economic exposure (figure 2b).

Figure 7. Tourism sector risk at NUTS2 level for the ssp126 and ssp585 scenarios in the years 2030 and 2050. Regions experiencing positive impacts are classified in the “no risk” category (white). Regions where data on either impact, exposure or vulnerability were not available are shown in grey.

3.4 Coastal and River flooding

Differently from the economic sectors assessed before, the risk of coastal and river flooding shows a weaker north-south gradient across the continent. For coastal flooding, risk significantly increases across the entire continent in the ssp585 scenario suggesting a strong correlation with the climate related forcing and sea-level rise (figure 8). Mediterranean regions appear as those at highest risk, with a hotspot also appearing in the regions bounding the Black Sea. Yet, high risk is also found in the oceanic regions of Iberia, as well as Scotland and most of the Baltic. These results are generally consistent with those of ESPON, which also identified relatively higher risk in the southern Mediterranean and the Black Sea, as well as the Southern Baltic regions.

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River flooding risk is the most unevenly spread across the continent, with hotspots appearing around the major river basins. River flooding exacerbates under ssp585 warming, but even the high mitigation scenario shows several regions at high risk by mid-century (figure 9). The projections show how eastern Europe is the hotspot of river flooding risk, with the regions of Romania being at high risk in all the studied scenarios. Most regions across Germany also appear at high to very high risk regardless of the level of warming. Southern Europe generally shows a lower risk profile for river flooding than the rest of the continent, with the few exceptions observed in northern Italy and Turkey. This is mainly due to the warming and drying effect produced by climate change in Southern Europe. While these regions are still subject to the risk of flash-flooding and the related hazards, these are projected to produce less damages than the large-scale flooding events caused by the overflowing of the riverine systems of central Europe affecting highly assets-dense areas.

Figure 8. Coastal flooding risk at NUTS2 level for the ssp126 and ssp585 scenarios in the years 2030 and 2050. Regions where data on either impact or vulnerability were not available are shown in grey.

Figure 9. River flooding risk at NUTS2 level for the ssp126 and ssp585 scenarios in the years 2030 and 2050. Regions where data on either impact or vulnerability were not available are shown in grey.

3.5 Aggregated Risk

Figure 10 shows the results of the aggregation of the sectorial risks addressed in this study in the four future scenarios considered. As for most individual sectors, a general increase in the aggregated risk index magnitude is observed later in the future and with higher greenhouse gas emissions. A notable difference between the colder and warmer scenarios is the level of risk in northern European regions, with several passing from “low risk” in SSP126 to “medium risk” in SSP585. In contrast, a similarity between all the studied scenarios is the identification of coastal regions across the continent as the most at risk. While the limited number of sectors considered might have led to a biased aggregated risk, with fishery productivity and coastal flooding risks only applying to coastal regions, this result highlights how coastlines are indeed disproportionately affected by climate change and suffer additional context-specific repercussions. Although it can be argued that the direct access to the sea represents a natural advantage in economic terms (i.e., tourism, commerce, fishery), this dependency from maritime activities might represent a burden for coastal regions under climate change. Indeed, while most coastal regions across Europe will be negatively impacted by climate change due to coastal flooding, only a few of them benefit significantly from maritime economic activities (EUROSTAT, 2024).

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Moreover, while it is true that other landscape-specific climate risks that are more applicable to inland regions have not been considered here, such as landslides or wildfires, these also affect many coastal regions around Europe.

To avoid biases resulting from missing data in specific sectors, aggregated results for NUTS2 regions in Türkiye, Norway, Switzerland and Iceland have been excluded and labelled in the map as “no data”. Still, aggregated results would effectively cover the whole EU27 region.

Figure 10. Aggregated risk at NUTS2-level for the ssp126 and ssp585 scenarios in the years 2030 and 2050. Regions where data on either impact, exposure or vulnerability in one or more sectors were not available are excluded from the aggregated analysis and shown in grey.

4. Conclusions

The aim of this deliverable was to produce an EU-wide integrated risk assessment at the NUTS2 level focusing on the most relevant sectors for TransformAr KCS and building on the biophysical impact assessment results of previous WP2 tasks. The results are meant to structure and support the Integrated Risk Assessment and prioritization of interventions TABs, and from there project exploitation processes such as Capitalisation, assessment and optimisation of adaptive blocks and solutions for building IPs (T6.3), Articulation and feeding of the CSA platform (T6.5), but also valuable solution for Transformative Adaptation in workshops with future solution buyers (D5.3) to discuss the operationalisation of alternative financing schemes. Results from D2.5 Integrated risk assessment will be included and available on the Transformar EU web data platform of Task 2.2. The analysis was structured according to an innovative risk framework based on the traditional IPCC risk assessment methodology and introducing the biophysical impact results as the primary driver for climate-related risks. This approach allowed a more comprehensive consideration of the multiple concomitant hazards contributing to climatic risks, going beyond the traditional one-hazard-one-risk approach followed by most climate risk assessments. In this perspective, risk was defined as the combination of climatic impact, socio-economic exposure and vulnerability, the latter encompassing the dimensions of sensitivity and adaptive capacity. Uncertainty emerging from different criteria to characterize hazards, either through single climate indicators or intermediate impact from biophysical models, are evaluated across different risk assessment products (d2.5 and d2.6) in the project. Availability of these products on the project web data platform will indicate to policy makers and allow to consider uncertainty between different risk assessment methods.

The analysis of the exposure and vulnerability components highlighted how the climatic risk gradients observed across Europe for most sectors often build on 1) the strong economic ties certain regions have with individual sectors and 2) high vulnerability stemming from a combination of relatively low social, institutional, infrastructural and economic development. In particular, the thematic analysis of the vulnerability components provided a good approximation of the regional level of attainment of some key indicators related to the SDGs.

The main message coming out of the risk analysis is that the least risk-prone regions tend to be those with a differentiated economy, making them less exposed to the sectorial damages brought by climate change, and with higher socio-technological development making them less vulnerable. Thus, these results can be used by stakeholders to promote a holistic approach to adaptation considering both the biophysical and the socio-economic dimensions, with equal attention posed on the prevention of physical impacts and the improvement of public welfare.

5. References

- Alfieri, L., Feyen, L., Salamon, P., Thielen, J., Bianchi, A., Dottori, F., & Burek, P. (2016). Modelling the socio-economic impact of river floods in Europe. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 16(6), 1401–1411. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-16-1401-2016>
- Barange, M., Bahri, T., Beveridge, M., Cochrane, K., Funge-Smith, S., & Poulain, F. (2018). *Impacts of Climate Change on Fisheries and Aquaculture. Synthesis of Current Knowledge, Adaptation, and Mitigation Options*.
- Becker, W., Saisana, M., Paruolo, P., & Vandecasteele, I. (2017). Weights and importance in composite indicators: Closing the gap. *Ecological Indicators*, 80, 12–22. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.03.056>
- Betts, R.A. and Brown, K. (2021). Introduction. In: The Third UK ClimateChange Risk Assessment Technical Report [Betts, R.A., Haward, A.B. and Pearson, K.V.(eds.)]. Prepared for the Climate Change Committee, London
- Bosello, F., Standardi, G., Parrado, R., Dasgupta, S., Guastella, G., Rizzati, M., Pareglio, S., Schleypen, J., Boere, E., Batka, M., Valin, H., Bodirsky, B., Lincke, D., Tiggeloven, T., & van Ginkel, K. (2020). D2.7. Macroeconomic, spatially-resolved impact assessment. Deliverable of the H2020 COACCH project. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5546248>
- Charron N., Lapuente V. and Bauhr M. (2024). “The Geography of Quality of Government in Europe. Subnational variations in the 2024 European Quality of Government Index and Comparisons with Previous Rounds”. QoG Working Paper Series 2024:2. Department of Political Science, University of Gothenburg. ISSN: 1653-8919.
- Cheung, W.W.L., Jones, M.C., Reygondeau, G., Stock, C.A., Lam, V.W.Y., Frolicher, T.L., (2016) Structural uncertainty in projecting global fisheries catches under climate change. *Ecol. Model.* 325, 57–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2015.12.018>.
- Cos, J., Doblas-Reyes, F., Jury, M., Marcos, R., Bretonnière, P.-A., & Samsó, M. (2022). The Mediterranean climate change hotspot in the CMIP5 and CMIP6 projections. *Earth System Dynamics*, 13(1), 321–340. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-13-321-2022>
- De Maio, F. G. (2007). Income inequality measures. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 61(10), 849–852.
- Dijkstra, L., Papadimitriou, E., Cabeza Martinez, B., De Dominicis., L and Kovacic, M. (2023). EU Regional Competitiveness Index 2.0. doi:10.2776/46106.
- European Environment Agency (2024). European Climate Risk Assessment. doi:10.2800/204249.
- EUROSTAT (2024). Tourism statistics at regional level. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Tourism_statistics_at_regional_level#Seasonality. Accessed: [12/09/204]. ISSN 2443-8219.

- Gallina, V., Torresan, S., Critto, A., Sperotto, A., Glade, T., & Marcomini, A. (2016). A review of multi-risk methodologies for natural hazards: Consequences and challenges for a climate change impact assessment. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 168, 123–132.
- Hidalgo, M., El-Haweet, A. E., Tsikliras, A. C., Tirasin, E. M., Fortibuoni, T., Ronchi, F., Lauria, V., Ben Abdallah, O., Arneri, E., Ceriola, L., Milone, N., Lelli, S., Hernández, P., Bernal, M., & Vasconcellos, M. (2022). Risks and adaptation options for the Mediterranean fisheries in the face of multiple climate change drivers and impacts. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 79(9), 2473–2488.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsac185>
- Hristov, J., Toreti, A., Pérez Domínguez, I., Dentener, F., Fellmann, T., C., E., Ceglar, A., Fumagalli, D., Niemeyer, S., Cerrani, I., Panarello, L., & Bratu, M. (2020) Analysis of climate change impacts on EU agriculture by 2050. In *EUR 30078 EN* (Issue 26). Publications Office of the European Union.
<https://doi.org/10.2760/121115>
- Jay, A. K., Crimmins, A. R., Avery, C. W., Dahl, T. A., Dodder, R. S., Hamlington, B. D., Lustig, A., Marvel, K., Méndez-Lazaro, P. A., Osler, M. S., Terando, A., Weeks, E. S., & Zycherman, A. (2023). Overview: Understanding risks, impacts, and responses. In A. R. Crimmins, C. W. Avery, D. R. Easterling, K. E. Kunkel, B. C. Stewart, & T. K. Maycock (Eds.), *Fifth National Climate Assessment*. U.S. Global Change Research Program. <https://doi.org/10.7930/NCA5.2023.CH1>
- Matei, N.A., García-León, D., Dosio, A., Batista e Silva, F., Ribeiro Barranco, R., Císcar Martínez, J.C., (2023) Regional impact of climate change on European tourism demand, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/899611, JRC131508.
- Magnan, A. K., Li, J., Tanguy, A., Hallegatte, S., & Buffet, C. (2025). The value of structured expert judgment to help assess climate adaptation. *Climate Risk Management*, 47, 100692.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2025.100692>
- Menk, L., Terzi, S., Zebisch, M., Rome, E., Lückerath, D., Milde, K., & Kienberger, S. (2022). Climate Change Impact Chains: A Review of Applications, Challenges, and Opportunities for Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessments. *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 14(2), 619–636.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1175/WCAS-D-21-0014.1>
- Navarro, D., Lizundia-Loiola, J., Paz, J., Abajo, B., Cantergiani, C., García, G. and Feliu E. (2022). *ESPON 2020 data and maps updates*. ISBN: 978-2-919816-65-1
- Palmer, T. E., Booth, B. B. B., & McSweeney, C. F. (2021). How does the CMIP6 ensemble change the picture for European climate projections? *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(9), 094042.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac1ed9>
- Papathoma-Köhle, M., Cristofari, G., Wenk, M., & Fuchs, S. (2019). The importance of indicator weights for vulnerability indices and implications for decision making in disaster management. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 36, 101103.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2019.101103>
- Pita, I., Mouillot, D., Moullec, F., & Shin, Y.-J. (2021). Contrasted patterns in climate change risk for Mediterranean fisheries. *Global Change Biology*, 27(22), 5920–5933.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15814>

- Simpson, N. P., Mach, K. J., Constable, A., Hess, J., Hogarth, R., Howden, M., Lawrence, J., Lempert, R. J., Muccione, V., Mackey, B., New, M. G., O'Neill, B., Otto, F., Pörtner, H. O., Reisinger, A., Roberts, D., Schmidt, D. N., Seneviratne, S., Strongin, S., ... Trisos, C. H. (2021). A framework for complex climate change risk assessment. In *One Earth* (Vol. 4, Issue 4, pp. 489–501). Cell Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.03.005>
- United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR). (2022). Projecting Effects of Climate Change in the framework of the INFORM Risk Index.
- Ye, B., Jiang, J., Liu, J., Zheng, Y., & Zhou, N. (2021). Research on quantitative assessment of climate change risk at an urban scale: Review of recent progress and outlook of future direction. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 135, 110415.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

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